

Mung straw management and nitrogen economy in rice culture

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Fertilizer use in multiple cropping systems requires a new strategy that will consider the lag in fertilizer production and consumption. Technology that helps maintain soil productivity in the intensive cropping system with moderate levels of fertilizer application must be evolved. In northwest India, the predominant crop rotation of rice - wheat is fertilizer-intensive. The new technology has made it possible to include summer

mung (*Vigna radiata*), a leguminous crop, as a catch crop in this cropping system. The wheat crop sown in early November and harvested in mid-April leaves sufficient time for sowing of summer mung, which matures in the third week of June. A study was undertaken to see the effect of plowing in of mung straw — after the pods have been picked — on nitrogen economy and yield of rice. The mung straw incorporated 1 day before rice is transplanted weighed 4.7 t/ha and added 100 kg N/ha. The soil of the experimental field was a Typic Ustochrept (sandy loam, pH 8.2, organic carbon content 0.17%) and contained 62, 3, and 72 kg available

N, P, and K/ha. The DTPA-extractable zinc, copper, iron, and manganese content of the air-dried soil was 1.5, 1.5, 13.2, and 3.0 ppm, respectively.

The plowing-in of mung straw, along with application of 60 kg N/ha, gave as much rice yield (6.9 t/ha) as that obtained with the application of 120 kg N/ha alone (see table). Incorporation of mung straw also caused a significant increase of organic carbon, and available nitrogen, copper, iron, and manganese contents. The study suggested that in soils of low organic matter content, plowing in of mung straw saved 60 kg N/ha in rice and also favored the natural supply of nutrients. ■

Effect of incorporation of mung straw on rice yield and soil properties, Ludhiana, India.

Straw and fertilizer (kg NP/ha) treatments		Grain yield (t/ha)	Organic carbon (%)	Available nutrients (kg/ha)			DTPA-extractable cations (ppm)			
Nitrogen	Phosphorus			Nitrogen	Phosphorus	Potassium	Zinc	Copper	Iron	Manganese
<i>Straw removed</i>										
60	0	5.1	0.19	69	4.5	72	0.71	0.64	15.4	3.1
60	30	5.0	0.21	69	9.6	73	0.94	0.71	19.3	4.3
120	0	6.9	0.21	69	4.7	78	0.87	0.75	17.6	4.0
120	30	7.2	0.22	72	10.6	86	0.94	0.68	17.6	3.0
Mean		6.1	0.21	70	7.5	77	0.87	0.70	17.5	3.6
<i>Straw plowed in</i>										
60	0	6.9	0.23	84	4.8	78	1.08	0.83	27.5	12.4
60	30	7.5	0.24	84	14.0	79	0.87	0.95	27.7	12.0
120	0	8.6	0.24	81	6.4	86	0.88	0.99	36.8	13.6
120	30	8.7	0.24	81	10.6	77	0.85	0.82	33.1	11.9
Mean		7.9	0.24	82	8.95	80	0.92	0.90	31.3	12.5
C.D. 5%										
Fertilizer		0.53	0.03	NS	NS	NS	NS	0.11	8.7	4.1
Straw		0.43	0.02	7	NS	NS	NS	0.04	7.1	6.9

Management trial for increasing nitrogen use efficiency of wetland rice

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Nitrogen use efficiency by wetland rice was studied during the 1978 and the 1979 dry seasons at Aduthurai. Soil type was clay loam, which had low available nitrogen, medium available phosphorus, and high available potash. Soil pH was 7.5. Nitrogen was applied at the rate of 60 kg/ha. Treatments were all basal vs split application of commercial urea, compared with deep placement of nitrogen as urea supergranules manufactured by IFFCO in India, urea enriched with neem cake and farmyard manure, and

granulated compost. The treatments had four replications set in a randomized block design.

Granulated compost recorded the maximum yield in both seasons (see

table). It was similar to commercial urea applied in two split doses (planting + panicle initiation or planting + tillering or tillering + panicle initiation), and neem cake-blended urea. ■

Effect of different methods of N application on rice yield at Aduthurai, India.

N source	N application (kg/ha)			Grain yield (t/ha)	
	Planting	Tillering	Panicle initiation	1978	1979
None	0	0	0	4.02	4.46
Commercial urea	60	0	0	4.63	4.84
Commercial urea	30	0	30	5.08	5.20
Commercial urea	30	30	0	5.00	5.12
Commercial urea	0	30	30	5.18	5.23
Neem cake-blended urea	60	0	0	5.05	5.16
Urea enriched with farmyard manure	60	0	0	4.40	4.58
1-g urea supergranules	60	0	0	4.73	4.67
2-g urea supergranules	60	0	0	4.40	4.58
Granulated compost	60	0	0	5.29	5.36
CD (0.05)				.51	.44